

DIPLOMA

TA'LIM FIDOYILARI

RESPUBLIKA ILMIY JURNALIDA

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**CURRENT STATE AND PROSPECTS OF DEVELOPMENT OF
CHILDREN'S TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN**

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

Bosh muharrir:
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MENTION
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